

THE ROLE OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN ENHANCING JOB SKILLS FOR PRODUCTION ECONOMY IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The graduates of higher educational systems eventually become the social and human capital resources of the society. Through systematic literature review and participant observation, this study identifies job skill deficiency among graduates of higher education institutions in Nigeria. Findings indicate that higher education institutions in Nigeria play a great role towards creating a production-oriented workforce. This study recommends the production economy orientation of students in our higher education system which will prepare these future leaders with the desired mindset to foster a production economy thereby achieving zero poverty (SDG 1), zero hunger (SDG 2) and promoting decent work and economic growth (SDG 8), in Nigeria. It concludes with a clarion call for a deeper research on the role of higher education institutions in enhancing job skills for production economy in Nigeria.

Keywords: climate action, higher education, job skills, production economy.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nigeria whose population is more of young people, should be expected to be more productive and development oriented. Research suggests that one of the greatest investments any society can make is in ensuring the well-being and educational development of its human resources especially the youths (Onnoghen et al, 2024; Anabaraonye, 2024). This is because they would eventually constitute the workforce. In Nigeria, the work force comprises of youths including middle and high skilled labour which are products of secondary and tertiary institutions. One of the main goals of Nigerian tertiary education is the acquisition of both physical and intellectual skills which will enable individuals to be self-reliant and useful members of the society (FRN, 2004). It is the statutory duty of the Nigerian higher education to groom the required human capital through relevant manpower training, abilities, attitudes, skills and knowledge (Babalola, 2007). If the workforce is production oriented, it implies that their productivity can contribute to the ranking of the country from developing to developed economy (Anabaraonye, Onnoghen, Nwafor & Obinna, 2024). Every developing economy has the potential to become a developed economy, which may depend on many factors in the country, including the role of higher education institutions in enhancing job skills of learners. Today's technological advancements for instance have disrupted many traditional employment options, portraying the modern work environment as fast and highly

dynamic, thus impacting the demand for skilled labour(Orji,2024). With over 200 million people and a mean age average of 17.5, Nigeria presents a formidable workforce that could drive economic growth and development. However, most of this workforce lacks the skills to successfully navigate the modern job market. A report from the National Bureau of Statistics in 2022 shows that 53.40% of youths in Nigeria are unemployed; this includes graduates(Orji,2024). This study highlights the role of higher education institutions in enhancing job skills for production economy in Nigeria.

2 METHODOLOGY

Materials used for this study were derived from peer reviewed academic journals, magazines, articles, conference papers, textbooks, and educational materials from libraries. The researchers gathered notable materials for the research but summarized the characteristics of the papers that centered more on “the role of higher education institutions in enhancing job skills for production economy in Nigeria”.

3 THE ROLE OF PRODUCTION ECONOMY IN ERADICATING POVERTY IN NIGERIA

Researchers have recently identified the role of entrepreneurship education in eradicating poverty, maximizing entrepreneurial opportunities and enhancing the production economy in Nigeria (Kolade et al,2022; Ufua et al,2021). When a country is bent on consumption economy instead of a production economy, poverty becomes inevitable. Poverty can be defined as the scarcity or the lack of a certain (variant) amount of material possessions or money. Poverty is a multi-faceted concept, which may include social, economic, and political elements. Absolute poverty, extreme poverty, or destitution refers to the complete lack of the means necessary to meet basic personal needs such as food, clothing and shelter(UNESCO, 2015). According to the World Bank, “Poverty is pronounced deprivation in well-being, and comprises many dimensions. It includes low incomes and the inability to acquire the basic goods and services necessary for survival with dignity. Poverty also encompasses low levels of health and education, poor access to clean water and sanitation, inadequate physical security, lack of voice, and insufficient capacity and opportunity to better one's life”(World Bank,2011). Some researchers in Nigeria identified climate change as one of the leading causes of poverty which negatively affects sustainable economic growth in Nigeria (Orji, Idika, Okeke, Anakwue, & Ntamu,2023).However, through enhancing green leadership and production economy, the impacts of change can be mitigated and eco-billionaires can be raised in Nigeria(Anabaraonye,2025).

4 ENHANCING PRODUCTION ECONOMY THROUGH EDUCATION

Climate change education is therefore very vital for enhancing climate resilience and fostering a production economy in Nigeria. A holistic approach must be adopted through proper climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies to address poverty and ensure sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. This includes enhancing climate resilience through imbibing of green entrepreneurial skills among the youths thereby advancing the production economy in Nigeria (Anabaraonye, Nwobu, Nwagbo, Ewa & Okonkwo, 2022). A production economy in Nigeria is crucial for economic growth and development, driving job creation, stimulating local markets, increasing government revenue, and promoting export diversification. It also helps reduce reliance on imports, fosters technological innovation, and contributes to overall improvements in the standard of living(Obasi, 2023). By producing locally, the manufacturing sector helps reduce

reliance on imports, saving foreign exchange and boosting domestic demand. Increased manufacturing output can lead to a wider range of exportable goods, diversifying the economy and earning more foreign exchange (Usoro, 2010). A focus on manufacturing can foster technological innovation and the development of skilled labor, essential for long-term economic competitiveness. Industrialization provides opportunities for training and upskilling the workforce, addressing the shortage of skilled labor in developing countries (Obasi, 2023).

5 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the discussion in this paper, the following areas of improvement are recommended to help bridge the performance standard gap, to address the issues of job skills deficiency, and poor production oriented mindset among graduates in Nigeria. These are:

1. Specialized teaching pedagogies such as problem solving, apprenticeship, field trip/excursion method, assignment and project management should be encouraged and utilized in the instructional process of higher education institutions in Nigeria.
2. Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES), internship, houseman ship which are championed by higher education institutions should be well implemented to achieve their set goals.
3. In the National Youth Service Camp, posting administrators should ensure corp members which are freshly baked from the higher education institutions in Nigeria are posted to organizations that can sharpen their job and employability skills.
4. Collaboration between the higher education institutions and labour market is needed in order to prepare students better for the real world of work.
5. University administration should supervise curriculum delivery and all teaching and learning programmes such as practical classes, field trips entrepreneurship, students individual work experience scheme (SIWES), internship houseman ship, to ensure that students receive the required experiences that can guarantee their job skill potential and production oriented mindset towards fostering a production economy.

6 CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

Suffice to emphasize that one of the milestones to achieve among our youth workforce is to inculcate a production-oriented mindset, a mindset to engineer a desirable change. It is a puzzle that Nigeria finds it a herculean task to progress from being a consumption economy to a production economy, despite her well-established potentials to become it. There is need to inculcate the desirable mindset into Nigerians through the higher education institutions. This is where the job skills and the orientation of mindset towards creation of production economy should be a cardinal objective of higher education institutions. Furthermore, there's a need for deeper research by researchers and scholars on the role of higher education institutions in enhancing job skills to foster production economy in Nigeria.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

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